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HUNGARIAN INDUSTRY-UNIVERSITY SHOWCASES

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Topics: New Notions of Interdisciplinarity in Engineering Education

Keywords: cooperation between academia and industry

The topic of the round-table discussion is cooperation between universities and industrial companies.

During the discussion we would like to highlight some good examples, how industry and universities can make joint project successfully.

Why is the session relevant?

Working together is not always easy as the two different types of organizations have different structure and different goals. The round-table will honestly talk about the challenges what we have and how we manage to overcome the difficulties.

How are session participants activated?

The participants of the round-table will discuss together the topic according to the next comments:

Szilasi Péter Tamás, head of Public Relations section, NEMAK:

The cooperation between NEMAK Győr and the Faculty of Material Science of the Miskolc University can be truly characterized as symbiotic.

It is not only about educational, scientific and research cooperation, but lot more saving a profession together.

It has an eight years history, when with the lead of Nematik, the Hungarian Association of Foundries ran a survey on the needs of the companies in the field of metal casting. The survey was on the research needs, and demand on highly trained professionals, engineers specialized on the metal casting and material science.

At that time secondary vocational training was fully missing, while the university level education was close to being extinct. Only one part time professor dealt with the topic. Research capacities were also almost close to none.

Based on the results the companies of the sector aligned their forces. They agreed to provide financial support to the Miskolc University, to help building up human capacities of the faculty and especially its institute focusing on automotive casting.

They also joined their forces to start dual education.

As a result of this program by now a small, but powerful institute is built up, with significant doctoral program, and 20-25 students enrolling to this highly specialized training on BSc level every year. The first dual training students had graduated this year. NEMAK have 2-4 dual training students every year, being the biggest dual training partner of the faculty.

There is a continuous and open discussion on the educational program and the execution of dual training. Starting the 5th year we are going to launch the 5th or 6th evolution of the training program. It is an ongoing joint learning.

There are also frequent occasions where we can feed our experiences back to the university as well as the other companies being involved in dual training.

NEMAK and Miskolc University also intensively join their forces in student recruitment, mutually helping in each other's activities.

NEMAK Győr highly depends on the scientific knowledge base of Miskolc University. Based on a yearly research contract usually 5-6 topics are worked out by the University. More and more the dual training students are joined in these researches. Giving them a real life topic for their studies and thesis work, but also providing extra research capacity to the University.

Frank Péter R&D Director, Knorr-Bremse:

Knorr-Bremse's Research & Development Center cooperates with universities since its founding in 1995. Our primary partners are among others, Budapest University of Technology (BME) and John von Neumann University Kecskemét.

We drive common research projects with universities and other research places, such as SZTAKI since the beginning. A special question here is the IP protection that can be resolved.

Knorr-Bremse together with its partners Mercedes and Kecskemét College launched Dual Education system in Kecskemét in 2012 as first in Hungary. Our extensive Student Program is a win-win-win for the student, university and the company. Besides that, Knorr-Bremse operates a PhD program.

Ács János, Manager, Partnering & Operations LEGO:

LEGO Manufacturing Kft. and BME Faculty of Logistics hosted a lesson for automatized logistics processes as joint venture. The lesson aimed to introduce a fully-automated high bay warehouse operations and a manufacturing site designed for material flow to university students while gather logistics related observations from them (external eyes and minds). Through this shared operations I can reflect on the pros and cons of collaboration between industrial and educational institutes.

Szűcs Lajos, Move Coordinator, Schaeffler:

Most of our new engineers are coming from the Faculty of Mechanical Engineering as fresh from college. However, in the technical training, the training material related to bearing manufacture has an insignificant part. To compensate for this - thanks to the good relationship with the Faculty of Engineering in Debrecen - the lecturers are constantly working with our engineers to improve the practical training. To strengthen the process we set up the Schaeffler optional course, where the students can gain a higher level of practical knowledge by solving project tasks. In addition, there has been another possibility in the training of lecturers, which is focusing on the education with more practical part, we have also had a practical lesson for economists, the results of that must be presented in their portfolio.

Pék Zoltán, Head of Sensor Development, Continental:**Cooperation of Pannonia University and Continental Veszprém**

In the recent years we had few common activities with the university however they were more like ad-hoc organised. We have been giving few lectures on Engineering faculty and also on Informatics faculty. This was not real help for the university and it had not given high value for the UNI students too.

In 2017 we decided to work out a complete unit called „ automotive software development in practice” for the Informatics faculty. The unit is organised for two semesters, consists of theoretical part and practice as well.

Continental nominated a team for giving the lectures and the practice furthermore the unit responsibility was taken by one of our engineers having PhD.

The theoretic part consists of methodologic part starting from requirement elicitation requirement decomposition, development, integration till verification. The theory also touches automotive standards especially Functional safety furthermore we give general introduction of the control functions like ABS, AYC, ACC and so on..

The practical part is building a robot vehicle and implementing one control function like Traction Control or A tempomat. The practice also covers the testing of the robot car in different conditions.

Our target with the unit is to get connected to the students and give them the chance to understand development process and methodology of safety critical items.

Today we offer the unit on Informatics and also on Engineering faculty. This semester 17 students signed in the unit.

This way we can contribute in the education of the students widening their view on product development getting more valuable knowledge with their degree. Furthermore we can increase our chance to welcome them on board at continental as employee.

Jakab Roland, Regional Director, ERICSSON:

Ericsson opened a complex hardware design research lab at the Budapest University of Technology and Economics a few years ago.

The cooperation has been working successfully, giving perfect place for the education as well as for PhD and diploma works. Once students approached us and asked whether they could use the Lab facilities when there is no education there. We said of course and as a result of this the lab contributed at large to the born of the first satellite of Hungary - MASAT.

The members of the round table session will share their experiences and explain why university and company relations getting more and more important:

1. companies can find the best and most talented students,
2. they can make important projects together (R&D)
3. the verve of the industry can teach students to be committed to deadlines, quality, responsibility and real solutions.